

HISTORY OF SHOTOKAN KARATE

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Bodhidharma was a Buddhist priest who is said to have been the transmitter of Zen (Chinese: Chan, Sanskrit: Dhyana, and English: meditation) to China. He was the third child of a Tamil king of the Pallava Dynasty. Bodhidharma is attributed with building up the acclaimed Shaolin School of Chinese Martial Arts which is referred to as Tripitaka Dharma Master. The records vary on the date of his appearance in China.

First, the book "**Anthology of the Patriarchal Hall**" describes that in 527, he visited Emperor Wu of Liang dynasty (**464-549**). "Anthology of the Patriarchal Hall" narrates him as the 28th Patriarch of Buddhism also.

The second record is found in the book "**Further Biographies of Eminent Monks,**" where it proclaims that Bodhidharma arrived in China at the time of the Liu Song dynasty (**420-479**).

BODHIDHARMA, AN INDIAN MONK. (The aforesaid photograph has been taken from

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His instructor, Prajnatarata, changed his name from Bodhitara to Bodhidharma. On Prajnatarata's death, Bodhidharma left his sanctuary in India to fulfil his teacher's last wish for going to China and spreading Buddhism. As per Chinese legends, he lived in a cave (near to shaolin temple) and gazed at a wall for 9 years and didn't speak for the entire duration. Presently, this cave is known as **Bodhidharma cave**. Then, he entered at Shaolin temple to teach monks a series of external exercises which are known as the Eighteen Arhat Hands (Shi-ba Lohan Shou), and an internal practice which is called the Sinew Metamorphosis Classic. His birthday is celebrated on the 5th day of the 10th lunar month every year. The well-known Sanchin Kata, consolidated today in over twelve Okinawan karate styles, is frequently ascribed legitimately to Bodhidharma.

BODHIDHARMA CAVE NEAR SHAOLIN TEMPLE, CHINA. (The aforesaid photograph

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This preparation strategy dependent on breathing systems and exposed knuckle or stick battling, spread later in China as **Kempo**. Bodhidharma wrote a book also, titled "**Ekin-Kyo**," which is considered as the first book based on the martial art. Bodhidharma invented a preparation technique to build the priests mentally and physically healthy at **Shaolin temple**. The Shaolin Monks got known as the best

contenders in China, and the method by which Bodhidharma instructed them was known as **Shaolin Kung Fu**. The Shaolin Monks went out of China to spread the fighting technology of Bodhidharma. Zen was promptly acknowledged in Japan.

SHAOLIN TEMPLE, CHINA. (The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.floatingzen.com and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.)

One of the most ardent devotees of the Buddhist religion was Sho Shin. His father was King Sho En, ruler of Okinawa, and **Sho Shin** became the King of Okinawa in **1477** when he was 13 years old. He was a religious person and, therefore, banned the use of weapons. This boycott was continued by the Satsuma faction also. This prompted the underground improvement of striking techniques and may have empowered unarmed battle strategies intended for use against protected troopers, for example, Jiu-jitsu.

Okinawa was an independent nation controlled by the Ryukyu Kingdom and thrived through trade with China. Ryukyu turned into a prefecture of Japan because of the Abolition of the Han System that happened in **1879**. During the Pacific War, Okinawa was the primary site for fighting techniques in Japan that was open to a common man too. There were three martial arts branches, namely **Shuri-te** (Sokon Matsumura: 1828-1898) which were hard techniques by kempo with offensive play. Secondly, **Naha-te** (Kanryo Higaonna: 1853-1916) which were softer techniques by Kempo with defensive plays through grappling, throws, and locks. Thirdly, **Tomari-te** (Kosaku Matsumora: 1829-1898) which were both soft and hard

techniques of Kempo. These were named after the Okinawan towns inside which they were created. Shuri town was both political centre and capital. Naha town was a big seaport and trade centre. Tomari town was a smaller seaport. They were referred to by and large as Okinawa-Te or To-De. To-De, the hand to hand fighting of Okinawa could articulate as 'kara,' which means empty and 'Te' means hand, thus, Funakoshi named it as KARATE. In the long run, these formed into two main styles, **Shorin-Ryu** that was created from Shuri and Tomari, was snappy and connected with natural breathing and was appropriate for physically light-build people. The other, **Shorei-Ryu** was originated from Naha which focused on constant, rooted motions with breathing synchronized with every movement and suitable for well-built people.

Karate was developed on the island of Okinawa, which lies in the south of the territory of Japan. After numerous years, the advancement of Karate as a method for self-protection increased in colossal ubiquity, as the Japanese government on the island had disallowed the utilization of weapons. Due to this national strategy, the self-protection procedures formed into an exciting Okinawan Karate specialty of "Karate" or "**void hand**" which involved only hand technique of combating at that time.

Karate is a hand technique right from its inceptions on the **Ryukyu Islands of Okinawa** in the East China Sea. The indigenous battling specialties of Okinawa were joined with hand-to-hand fighting of the neighboring nations, for example the White Crane style from Fujian, China. A significant number of the modern Karate styles began in Okinawa, which Japan used to administer. Okinawa is near "**Fuzhou**" a city in China. It is believed that combative techniques came to Okinawa through 'Fuzhou' by traders and tourists. As it is the traditional meeting point of Chinese and Japanese cultures, Okinawa became the place where the Okinawa Karate started to take shape in the mid-1800s and was known as '**Toudi**' (Tang Hand, China Hand) or just Te (Hand). The most dedicated experts in Okinawa were individuals from the illustrious court in support of the Ryukyu lord. These pioneers of Karate were liable for keeping harmony and ensuring the safety of the imperial family, which generally tried their procedure. The coaching of Karate during this period was troublesome because of Japanese control on the Ryukyu kingdom, where the Japanese restricted the ownership of weapons and the act of Karate strategies. Therefore, Karate's work during this time was regularly led stealthily, around evening time, and in isolated territories. A significant number of the Kata we practice today were created or refined during this time.

Legendary Grandmaster Gichin Funakoshi is generally viewed as the "Father" of modern Karate because of his endeavors to acquaint territory of Japan with the Okinawan Karate, from where it spread to the rest of the world. He was born on November 10, 1868, in Yamakawa, Shuri (Okinawa Prefecture). Being born into a family that had run into some bad luck implied that he spent his youth with his maternal grandparents. He started as a weakling, wiped out and in unexpected frailty, whose guardians carried him to Master Itosu for his karate preparation. His doctor, Tokashiki recommended certain herbs that would rejuvenate him. Soon Funakoshi got healthier. Master Gichin took coaching from Yasutsune Itosu in the initial stage of learning Karate. Funakoshi prepared with Azato stealthily since the Okinawans had their weapons prohibited and had to practice secretly. Master Funakoshi used to live in a small room with his students at Suidobata, Tokyo. He used to clean the dormitory during the day when the students were in their classes and take Karate classes at night. He made companion at school with the oldest child of the thenpopular karate ace, Master Azato Anko and through this kinship, he was acquainted with Karate. His style of Karate started from him having prepared under two renowned Okinawan Karate experts, Master **Azato Anko** (1827-1906) and Master **Itosu Anko** (1831–1915). This art charted an impressive course of his life. He had become well-known in Ryukyu-style hand-to-hand fighting soon. As throughout the years he sought after his preparation and ceaselessly built up his wonderful aptitudes, Master Funakoshi accepted a job as an associate teacher at the primary school at the age of 20, in **1888**. He soon became Chairman of the Okinawa Martial Arts Society.

In 1898, karate was resolved to be no danger to the legislature and was permitted to be exhibited and rehearsed openly. Master Itosu is credited with encouraging the first Karate class at the Shurijijo Elementary School in Okinawa.

In 1901, Karate training was legitimized in Okinawa, and its investigation got required in center schools. Being sure of consent from Azato and Itosu, Funakoshi declared that he would start officially educating Karate. Now he was 33 years old.

In 1902, when **Shintaro Ogawa**, the Commissioner of school education in the Kagoshima Prefecture, having seen a presentation of Karate given by Master Funakoshi, presented a report to the Ministry of Education in Japan about the advantages of the preparation in karate, Karate turned into a part of the educational plan in schools and started to be polished uninhibitedly in Japan.

In 1916, the historical Shotokan karate really started with Master Gichin Funakoshi's trip to Kyoto, where karate was shown without precedent for Japan, at the Butokuden. While the showing was effective and the

Japanese were highly intrigued, there was no prompt race to carry the Okinawan art to Japan on a conventional premise. Although impressed with it, the Japanese, despite everything, would in general be dubious of anything simply Okinawan, and they thought that it was convenient to see karate as a fascinating sideshow. This mentality could have been the end of karate in Japan had it not been for a serendipitous occasion on **March 6, 1921**. On that day, the Crown Prince (the Emperor Hirohito) of Japan visited Okinawa while on his visit to Europe. Looking to impress the Prince with the rich culture of Okinawa, the Department of Education asked Funakoshi to give a karate show for him in the **Great Hall of Shuri Castle, Okinawa, Japan**. So entranced was the ruler by the exhibition that he talked about it enthusiastically all through the remainder of his journey. In this manner the Ministry of Education officially mentioned a karate show be performed at the main National Athletic Exhibition in Tokyo. Funakoshi was obviously picked to perform. It made a strong positive impression on the Japanese public also. The Japanese government appreciated this new way. From that point onwards, Karate turned out to be exceptionally prevalent and spread quickly in Japan. During Funakoshi's exhibition, he had made his Karate enthusiasts be dressed in a similar Gi as the Judo students do; at that point, he put the belts on them and had them show significant accomplishments. He renamed the technique from "To-Te Jutsu" (the method of the Chinese hand) to "Karate-do" (the technique for the Empty Hand).

SHURI CASTLE, NAHA, OKINAWA, JAPAN. (Photo by CEphoto, Uwe Aranas. The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.commons.wikimedia.org and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.)

He spread the specialty of Karate-do with endless enthusiasm, and this made him considerably fruitful. Now, Funakoshi turned into an exceptionally well-educated Master. Funakoshi additionally functioned as a calligraphist and creator, expanding his works under the pen name of "**Shoto**." He was notable in Japan and progressively found new Karate adherents from various colleges.

In 1922, at the age of 54, he presented Okinawan Karate-Jutsu before the Ministry of Education, Japan. This presentation, the first-ever open showcase of Karate-Jutsu in Japan, was a dazzling achievement. Promptly, the founder of Judo, **Master Jigoro Kano** and his student, **Gima Shinkin**, welcomed Master Funakoshi to give a presentation of Kata. Remarkably, Master Funakoshi was requested from all sides to remain in Tokyo. Energized by the chance to further advance the Karate that he had accomplished to such a great deal, in Japan, Master Funakoshi started showing it at Tokyo's Meiseijuku quarters for Okinawan. Here, it is important to emphasize that Master Jigoro Kano was the only man who invented **Judo-gi** which was derived from the **KIMONO** dress, a Japanese traditional garment and later Master Funakoshi adopted and invented new **Karate-gi** which was lighter in weight than Judo-gi. In 1922, Funakoshi published a book entitled "**Ryukyu Kempo: Karate**," which has the honor of being the first-ever book in the history of Karate and quickly made an exceptional Karate success.

KIMONO DRESS WORN BY A JAPANESE WOMAN. (The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.yoycart.com and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.)

The emblem for Shotokan Karate, "**The tiger in the circle**" or "**Tora no maki**" or "**The tiger roll,**" was planned by the well-known artist **Hoan Kosugi** (December 30, 1881- April 16, 1964), a companion of Master Funakoshi, to represent his books about Karate. The emblem is generally utilized and received all-inclusively by Shotokan Karate club affiliations till now. Respectfulness, regard, and the protective qualities of Karate, which were secured as the fundamental topics in Funakoshi's standards, are altogether symbolized in the logo of Shotokan Karate. The tiger in the circle outlines the rules of Karate-do. The tiger represents the capacity to battle and win, yet the limits of the circle constrain its

opportunity and forcefulness. The ring speaks of tolerance, though, sensibility, knowledge and control are the core of Karate-do.

SHOTOKAN EMBLEM

ARTIST HOAN KOSUGI

World War-II during 1939-1945, unleashed destruction on the whole world and the Karate world was specifically affected badly. Precious records of the history and legacy of Karate were lost during the attack on Okinawa; many Japanese Karatekas lost their lives attempting to safeguard their nation.

In 1922, Master Gichin Funakoshi, acquainted the people of Japan more with Karate during the 1st National Athletic Exhibition held in Tokyo. The exhibition ended up being an extraordinary accomplishment because of the rising fame of Master Funakoshi. He showed just a single strategy, a complete discipline, which spoke to a blend of Okinawan styles. This strategy was known as Shotokan.

Shotokan incorporates Kanji symbols in the Japanese language as **SHOTO-KAN**, which was picked by Funakoshi's students to name his first close-to-home **dojo**, and it gets its name from his pseudonym, '**Shoto**,' signifying '**Pine Waves**,' and '**Kan**,' which means '**House**,'.

In 1924, Funakoshi was requested by Professor Shinyo Kasuya of the German Language Department to teach Karate at **Keio University**. The Keio University authorities were so impressed by the teachings of Master Funakoshi that they established the Karate-do Club at Keio University. Later, many Japanese Universities had Karate clubs where research of Karate used to be conducted that brought Karate to the modern era. The Keio, Waseda, Hosei, and Takushoku represent the top Karate colleges in Japan, with the highest social and political

status. As the prevalence of Karate-Jutsu started to spread, Master Funakoshi created the first-ever "**DAN Ranking Certification**" in April 1924. During this period, Funakoshi and his son Yoshitaka or Gigo Funakoshi included Kumite (battling) techniques, the Japanese KYU/DAN Ranking System, and a portion of the conventional ideas of Budo (Martial Way) to the framework. Around the same time, with the support of his instructor of Buddhism, **Abbot Furukawa Gyodo** (1872-1961) of Engakuji Temple in Kamakura, Master Funakoshi began rehearsing Zen. He was requested to advance the Okinawan Karate in the rest of Japan. Master Funakoshi blended a total arrangement of techniques and hypotheses and changed the Chinese and Okinawan names of the Kata into standard Japanese.

In 1929, after much ideation and reflection, he additionally changed the name of Karate-Jutsu (Chinese-hand Karate technique) to Karatedo (the method for Karate, or the way for the empty hand). He, at that point, characterized the "**Twenty precepts of Karate**" and built a fantastic Karate reasoning. Finally, the method for Karate had made its mark and was picking up ubiquity the whole way across Japan.

KEIO UNIVERSITY, JAPAN. (Photo by Kakidai-own work. The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.commons.wikimedia.org and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.)

In 1930, Funakoshi further expanded Karate studies in Japan. The colleges were the significant destinations of Karate study, and they were impacted by research on physiology and workout. Under Yoshitaka, the improvement of Shotokan Karate truly quickened that brought straightforwardness in the intensity of punching and kicking methods. This learning consolidated into the Kihon (essentials) of Shotokan Karate. During the 1930s, Karate's further styles, Goju-Ryu, Shito-Ryu, and Wado-Ryu, had been created notwithstanding the form of Shotokan Karate. These styles were additionally presented by Masters from Okinawa, which are as follows:

1. **Shito-Ryu (Japan)**, which was established by Master Kenwa Mabuni in 1928, and was based on practicing a lot of Kata to bring out perfection instances.
2. **Goju-Ryu (Okinawa)**, which was formed by Master Chojun Miyagi in 1930, and was based on using circular block and Jujitsu techniques.
3. **Shoto-Ryu (Japan)**, which was defined by Master Gichin Funakoshi in 1938, and was based on doing wide stances that deliver powerful attacks rapidly on an opponent.
4. **Wado-Ryu (Japan)**, which was created by Master Hironori Otsuka in 1939, and was based on a natural posture to dodge the assailant's attack or to make it minimize.

On January 29, 1936, the first official Shotokan Dojo "Dai-Nihon Karatedo Shoto-Kan" was opened in Zoshigaya, Mejiro, Tokyo. Japanese Karate-ka contributed funds to manufacture the main building of Karate dojo, which they named Shotokan in regard of Funakoshi Sensei. Unfortunately, it was demolished by an allied forces' air attack on April 29, 1945. Under Master Funakoshi, the first Shihans (Senior teachers) were **Takeshi Shimoda** (1901-1934), Master's first remarkable student, who died in 1934 at a young age and **Yoshitaka Funakoshi** (1906-1945) who died young in 1945. The number of individuals wishing to start practice was increasing day by day. The Katas modified to adjust to a dynamic new style. After being seen by the Japanese Ministry of Education during a Karate exhibit, Funakoshi approached it to carry his Karate to colleges in Japan for guidance. His presentation of the Karate technique was successful there and he sent forward an assortment of extraordinary students, like Takagi and Nakayama of Nippon Karate Kyokai, Yoshida of Takudai, Obata of Keio, Noguchi of Waseda, and Otsuka, the organizer of Wado-Ryu karate to different colleges and universities in some territories of Japan.

After the 2nd World War residue settled in **1945**, one of Master Funakoshi's top students, Masatoshi Nakayama started to sort out the rest of the students and recoup the lost preparing strategies of Kata and Kumite. Gichin Funakoshi assumed a significant job in acquainting Japan with karate from Okinawa, acclimated to decrease injury and converged with approaches for athletic preparation. There were some senior students of Master Funakoshi including Masatoshi Nakayama, Isao Obata, and Hidetaka Nishiyama who wanted to form an organization which would be dedicated to the promotion, education, management and research of Karate. Therefore, on **May 27, 1949** an organization was formed which is known as **Nihon Karate Kyokai or Japan Karate Association (JKA)**. This organization was totally dedicated to Master Funakoshi's endeavors. Master Funakoshi was appointed as the supreme commander of the JKA and Hidetaka Nishiyama was appointed as the Chief Instructor. The Japan Karate Association (JKA) started framing rules for Karate challenges, including a focus on Kata and Kumite. These rivalries aligned Karate closer with different indigenous Japanese hand-to-hand fights, for example, kendo and judo. Today, Karate-do is spread over several nations around the globe. He needed to clarify that the essential tutoring and preparation must be the significant prime point. At this point, Master Funakoshi had, for quite some time, been instructing Karate to secondary school and college students. Subsequently, Karate clubs had jumped up at advanced education foundations all over Japan, which is another motivation behind why Karate has moved towards being regarded as it is today.

In May 1949, a few of the first Shotokan Karate Masters split from the JKA association. One of these was **Hirokazu Kanazawa** (May 3, 1931 – December 8, 2019), known as "Kancho." Kanazawa was the protege of the late superintendent of the Shotokan style, Masatoshi Nakayama, and was one of the only a handful few outstanding Karate experts who contemplated under Master Gichin Funakoshi himself.

On April 10, 1957, the Ministry of Education, Japan, gave legal recognition to the JKA, turning it into a rightful institute. After sixteen days past this recognition, Master Funakoshi passed away on **April 26, 1957** at the age of 89. An enormous open remembrance was held at the Ryogoku Kokugikan (Ryogoku National Sumo Hall), which included 20,000 individuals, including numerous sports celebrities and government officials that came to offer their tribute. A commemoration landmark to Master Funakoshi was built up at **Engakuji Temple in Kamakura, Japan**. **On April 29**, every year, the date of the Shoto Festival, individuals from the JKA pay a

privileged visit to this memorial. A commemoration to Gichin Funakoshi was raised by the Shotokai at Engakuji, a monastery in Kamakura, on December 1, 1968. Designed by **Kenji Ogata** the landmark highlights calligraphy by Funakoshi and **Sogen Asahina** (1891–1979), the main priest of the monastery which bears the words "**Karate ni sente nashi**," which means "**There is no first attack in Karate.**"

GRANDMASTER GICHIN FUNAKOSHI MEMORIAL AT ENGAKUJI TEMPLE, KAMAKURA, JAPAN.

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The JKA had already started its well-known educator training project and started to create the absolute, most capable, gifted, and formidable Karate specialists on the planet. Ace Nakayama utilized the educator course to spread the humble Okinawan Karate worldwide. Remarkable educators from the JKA instructional classes included Masters **Hidetaka Nishiyama** (October 10, 1928 – November 7, 2008), **Teruyuki Okazaki** (June 22, 1931 – April 21, 2020), **Yutaka Yaguchi** (November 14, 1932), **Hirokazu Kanazawa** (May 3, 1931 – December 8, 2019), **Keinosuke Enoda** (July 4, 1935 – March 29, 2003), **Takayuki Mikami** (January 1, 1933), **Tetsuhiko Asai** (June 7, 1935 – August 15, 2006), and numerous others. These incredible educators formed the universe of Karate work during the height of its ubiquity during the 1960s and 1970s. During the 1st Japanese Master's Championship in 1957, as indicated in the reports by the JKA Instructor Teruyuki Okazaki, he was providing guidance in the Central Dojo of the JKA consistently, straight up to a couple of days before his death. The JKA proceeded with the spreading of Shotokan Karate with Funakoshi's point, with overall accomplishment

under the initiative of Masatoshi Nakayama. Nakayama set down the required measures for the procedures, groupings, and use of the Shotokan Kata in his books, which are followed till now.

ENGAKUJI TEMPLE, KAMAKURA, JAPAN. (Photo by Andrea Schaffer from Sydney, Australia. The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.commonswiki.org and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.)

The 1st JKA All Japan Karate Championship was held in **October 1957** in Tokyo. When this yearly competition's framework was setting up, it wasn't long before there were many JKA karate branches in towns, schools, and renowned colleges in Japan. **In 1958**, Master Nakayama was delegated as the Chief Instructor. **In 1961**, His Majesty, the Crown Prince of Japan (presently His Majesty the Emperor of Japan), went to attend the fifth JKA All Japan Karate Championship. The JKA karate had become noticeable. This period saw dynamic advancement in the art of Karate. As a consequence of consistent coaching among educators, the complete framework of Karate was formed. For the first time, the best forms for each Kumite position, stance, and action merged in a proper scientific way. There was a clear distinction between the "correct" and "incorrect" approach to execute every technique, position, punch, and kick. When these methods were created, several teachers went abroad to spread Karate's specialty around the globe. The JKA was the principal karate association to set up dojo outside Japan. That's why the JKA is so famous and influential in the world. During this period, the JKA further built up its karate guidance framework and keeping in mind the incredible growth of its branch dojo all through Japan, it started sending some of its most

exceptionally trained, proficient educators to America, Europe, and the Middle East to instruct and build up the dojo. Karate was turning into success outside Japan as well. Moreover, the JKA turned into the leading karate association to send its certified full-time educators to demonstrate Karate in colleges.

In 1975, by acknowledging Karate's entry into the Olympics as a top priority, the first universal competition supported by the JKA, the IAKF (International Amateur Karate Federation) World Cup was held in the U.S., and it continued for the three more times later also. Notwithstanding, to safeguard the whole system and soul of IpponShobu (bringing down the adversary with one blow), the JKA organized another competition, the first-ever worldwide Shoto World Cup Karate Championship Tournament in 1985 and that was a declaration of how much global a martial technique Karate had become.

Ace **Teruyuki Okazaki** and **Hidetaka Nishiyama** (October 10, 1928 – November 7, 2008), were instructed by the JKA in 1961, to spread Shotokan Karate in the USA. **In 1977**, Ace Okazaki built up the "**International Shotokan Karate Federation**" (**ISKF**) in Philadelphia which was assigned the overall central command. The ISKF ceaselessly developed and thrived as a part of the Japan Karate Association (JKA) until 2007, setting up an Instructor Training Institute in the USA to reflect the JKA training program.

In 1978, Hirokazu Kanazawa (1931–2019), 10th Dan, split away from the JKA and formed **Shotokan Karate-do International Federation (SKIF)**.

Kanazawa had trained under Masatoshi Nakayama and Hidetaka Nishiyama who were the two students of legend Gichin Funakoshi. SKIF presented components of TAI-CHI, especially in the matter of balance, and effectively advanced the development of Shotokan art. Kanazawa is viewed as one of the most splendid Shotokan master. Most prominently, he won the kumite title at the main JKA Open Tournament (in 1957) with a wrecked hand. Kanazawa was granted 10th Dan in 2000. Established in **October, 1978** with over two million individuals in 103 nations around the world, the SKIF is the world's most prominent Shotokan Karate association. Shotokan Karate is one of the most prevalent of the present-day styles. It is the most dominant and dynamic of Japanese techniques. In his late 70's, Master Hirokazu Kanazawa was the Chairman and Chief Instructor of the Shotokan Karate-do International Federation (SKIF) and was holding the evaluation of 10th DAN.

Master Masatoshi Nakayama (April 13, 1913 – April 15, 1987), who became the second Chief Instructor of the JKA after Sensei Funakoshi died in November 1957,

was the only man to spread Karate worldwide in the **1960s and 1970s** and put it on a scientific method through Kinesiology, Anatomy, Psychology, and Physics associated with Karate techniques. He had started learning Karate under the incredible ace Gichin Funakoshi in 1931. After moving on from Takushoko University in 1937, he had gone to Peking to learn the Chinese language, where he also examined different styles of Chinese fighting techniques there. He also published various books, including "Dynamic Karate," a top to bottom scientific method of Kihon, and several videos of specialized and pragmatic data on Kata, Kihon, and Kumite. Sensei Masatoshi Nakayama held the position of 10th Dan at the age of 74. When Master Nakayama died, the JKA suffered disturbances, continuing for two decades.

In 1986, Nobuyuki Nakahara (Born on December 11, 1934), a recognized business tycoon and former Tokyo University Karate Club partner, was delegated as the 8th Chairman of the JKA. Japan Karate Association (JKA) is a top and reputed Karate organization at the international level. Masters who represent the JKA Shotokan Karate at a global scale, are **Taiji Kase** (February 9, 1929 – November 24, 2004) from the European branch in Paris, **Hideki Ochi** in Germany, **Hiroshi Shirai** in Italy, **Keinosuke Enoda** (July 4, 1935 – March 29, 2003) in Great Britain, **Satoshi Miyazaki** (June 17, 1938 – May 31, 1993) in Belgium, **Higashino** in Brazil, **Ishiyama** in Venezuela, **Stan Schmidt** (the first nonJapanese fifth dan) in South Africa, **Hideki Okamoto** (July 30, 1941– April 30, 2009) in Syria and Lebanon, **Masahiko Tanaka** (born on February 24, 1941) in Denmark, **Sasaki** in the Philippines, **Hiroshi Matsuura** in Mexico, and others. Around 5,000,000 individuals currently rehearse the JKA Shotokan karate-do in almost every nation in the world. The command of the JKA is to add to world harmony by directing exploration and giving Karate-do guidance. It aims at affecting youngsters and teenagers to improve their physical and emotional well-being just as developing the soul of combative techniques and the idea of Japanese martial art which highlights behaviour and honour.

In 1990, the official status of the JKA was in a crisis when a few of its segregated members unlawfully changed the executive register. It faced a massive disaster for a long time. The Japan Supreme Court rejected these separated members' appeal in **June 1999** and closed the case forever. During this period, the JKA continued its progress under the instructions of the Chief Instructor Master **Sugiura Motokuni** (October 4, 1924 – August 10, 2015). With its lawful status re-established by court decisions, the JKA jumped into the 21st Century. It re-built its interior association and

revamped its monetary base. **In December 2000**, it bought land and set up its new central command and dojo in the centre of Tokyo. The fantastic opening function was held in **May 2001**, by various dignitaries and numerous individuals from other karate associations. With recharged power, the JKA repositioned itself, plainly characterizing itself as "**The Keeper of Karate's Highest Tradition.**" **In 2004**, the JKA introduced an official website, through which it proceeds, as usual, to advance genuine Karate around the globe.